

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES IN THE PRESENCE OF MICRO-SIZED VOIDS

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, three glass/epoxy cross-ply laminates were produced by liquid resin infusion by changing some process variables, possibly leading to lower production costs but also to the presence of voids. Uniaxial fatigue tests were carried out focusing on the initiation and propagation of transverse cracks and on the crack density evolutions.

Comparisons between specimens without and with voids revealed a strong detrimental effect of voids on fatigue crack initiation, propagation and on the crack density evolution.

This represents the first step towards the development of a model linking the manufacturing costs to the presence of defects and the fatigue performances, that is being developed by the composite research group of the Department of Management and Engineering of the University of Padova. This will be an important tool for the optimisation of the manufacturing process and the reductions of the cost of a composite part.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thanks to their outstanding mechanical properties combined with low density, composite materials have undergone a wide development in many industrial fields in the last decades. In fact many structural parts made of composite materials are employed in the aeronautical, naval, automotive and wind energy industries.

However, the main obstacle to the diffusion of composite materials to the large scale production is the quite high cost, not only due to the materials themselves, but mainly due to the absence of predictive models and well defined design procedures.

This fact forces companies in expensive and time consuming experimental and prototyping activities. Accordingly, one of the main goals of the scientific community is to provide predictive models and reliable design procedures for industrial applicability to decrease the costs of the design phase.

In addition the optimisation of the manufacturing process has a fundamental role in decreasing the cost of structural composite parts. The choice of process variables has a direct influence both on the manufacturing costs and, in view of the possible introduction of manufacturing defects, on the fatigue performance, the latter being the major driver for the in-service and maintenance costs.

The optimisation of the manufacturing process requires the knowledge of the relationship between process variables and the presence of defects, as well as the link between type and amount of defects and fatigue performance. The most typical defect in composite laminates is represented by voids.

The presence of voids is detrimental for static [1-5] and fatigue [6-14] properties of composites. Concerning fatigue behaviour, S-N curves were found to be steeper and shifted towards shorter fatigue life in presence of voids [8-11] both under tension-tension and compression-compression loading conditions. This was found also under bending loads for unidirectional [7,11] and woven laminates [6].

A linear trend was reported by Lambert et al. [12] between the fatigue life of [0/45/-45]_{3s} laminates and the size of the largest defect in critical positions. Conversely no clear trend was evident between fatigue life and global void content or the largest defect in the whole specimen [12].

An interesting, though qualitative, analysis of fatigue damage evolution, allowed Lambert and co-authors [12] to identify which were the critical plies in which the presence of voids played a deleterious role.

In their study of the inter-laminar tensile strength (ILTS) under fatigue, Seon et al. [13] correlated the life reduction under cyclic loading to the presence of a single void in critical position.

Recently, Sisodia and co-authors [14] analysed damage evolution in multidirectional laminates under fatigue loading, showing that the density of off-axis cracks, and the subsequent stiffness degradation, were higher in the presence of voids.

Most of the experimental investigations in the literature deal with specific laminate configurations and aim at characterising the influence of voids on the total fatigue life, without providing quantitative data on damage evolution, which would be important to be considered.

In fact, the fatigue life of multidirectional laminates is characterised by a progressive damage evolution beginning with the initiation and propagation of off-axis cracks [15,16].

As the number of cycles is increased the crack density and length increase causing the degradation of the global elastic properties.

As the stiffness is often a fundamental parameter in the design of composite parts, understanding the influence of voids on damage evolution, instead of the final failure only, is fundamental.

This means characterising the influence of voids on the cycles spent for the initiation of the first cracks, on the through-the-width crack propagation and crack density evolution.

In addition the analysis of the influence of voids on the damage mechanisms responsible for crack initiation and propagation is fundamental for defining reliable predictive models.

In this frame the aim of the present work is to understand the effect of some important parameters related to the liquid resin infusion process on the presence of defects, and subsequently to characterise the influence of such defects on fatigue crack initiation, propagation and crack density evolution.

To this aim cross-ply laminates were manufactured with different process parameters and tested under fatigue loading.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cross-ply laminates with lay-up $[0/90_2]_s$ were manufactured by means of the liquid resin infusion process.

Unidirectional glass fibres UT-E500 by Gurit were adopted as reinforcements, whereas the matrix system was composed by RIMR-235 resin and RIMH-235 hardener by Momentive.

Resin (400g) and hardener (134g) were mixed for 3 minutes at 300 rpm with a DISPERMAT TU shear blender from VMA-Getzman. For producing the first laminate the mixing was followed by extensive degassing of the resin (at 0.05 mbar for 20 minutes), to consistently reduce the amount of air entrapped in the resin during the mixing.

Then the 300x200 mm laminate was infused with an outlet pressure of 0.05mbar, while the inlet pressure was continuously adjusted by the operator during the infusion process to control the speed of the resin and ensure the best filling of the mould.

The laminates were cured at room temperature for three days and then post-cured in an oven for 12 hours at 60°C.

A second laminate was then manufactured with the only difference that the resin was not degassed after mixing. This led to saving in the infusion time (20 minutes for a 6-layers 300x200 laminate), but also to the presence of voids, as shown in the edge view of Figure 1. From the edge of the specimens an average void area fraction (A_v) of 0.34% was calculated, whereas no voids were found in the degassed specimens. The average void diameter was equal to 44 μ m.

A third laminate was manufactured with non degassed resin and keeping a constant inlet pressure of 1bar during the entire infusion process.

This third process leads to lower production costs as it does not require the constant presence of an operator. In this case much more voids were found, as shown in Figure 2, with an average void area fraction of 6.7% and an average diameter of 45 μ m.

Figure 1: Voids in the second panel

Figure 2: Voids in the third panel

From the infused panels 23 mm-wide specimens were cut and polished on the edges.

Fatigue tests were performed by means of a MTS 858 MiniBionix hydraulic machine. An axial extensometer MTS632.29F-30 with an initial length of 25 mm was mounted to monitor the stiffness during the tests. Cycles were applied in load control with a frequency of 10 Hz and a load ratio

(minimum to maximum cyclic load) of 0.05. Four load levels were considered, corresponding to a global applied stress of 50, 60, 70 and 80 MPa, apart from the third panel for which tests at 80 MPa were not carried out.

Exploiting the glass/epoxy specimens translucency, and with the aid of a lightening system mounted behind the specimen, damage was monitored by taking periodical pictures of the coupons in an observation region of 57 mm length. Analysing the pictures allowed us to count and measure the transverse cracks and thus to characterise the life to crack initiation, the crack density evolution and the crack growth rate.

3 FATIGUE TESTS RESULTS

The first observable event of damage was the initiation of transverse cracks in the 90° ply. Cracks were seen to initiate both at the edges and on the central part of the specimens and stably propagated in the width direction.

The S-N curves for the initiation of the first crack in every specimen are shown in Figure 3, where a dramatic detrimental effect of the presence of voids can be observed.

Figure 3: S-N curves for the initiation of the first crack

As highlighted in Refs. [15,16], if cracks are far enough from each other they propagate without interacting and in a steady state manner. This means that the Energy Release Rate (ERR) is not a function of the crack length and therefore the crack propagation rate is constant. This phenomenon was observed also for the specimens under analysis, as proven by the crack propagation curve in Figure 4 exhibiting a linear trend, the slope of the straight line representing the crack growth rate.

It was calculated that the crack growth rate for the specimens with $A_v = 0.34\%$ is about 75% higher than that for the void-free specimens at the same stress level, highlighting the detrimental effect of voids also on crack propagation.

Because of the high void content the specimens of the third panel were not very translucent and therefore only results concerning the first crack initiation (not propagation) are reported.

Figure 4: Crack propagation curves for a specimen without voids tested at 70 MPa

As previously mentioned the crack density (number of cracks per unit length) increased with the number of cycles. An example of crack density evolution for specimens of the first two panels is shown in Figure 5 for a stress state of 80 MPa. As expected the crack density increases much more steeply and reaches saturation much earlier in the specimen containing voids.

Figure 5: Crack density evolution at 80 MPa

4 CONCLUSIONS

Three cross-ply laminates were manufactured by means of the liquid resin infusion process. For the first one the matrix was degassed prior to infusion and the inlet pressure was continuously adjusted during the process to ensure the best filling of the mould. For the second laminate the same parameters were adopted but the resin was not degassed. Eventually the third laminate was infused by keeping the inlet pressure constant, which did not require the presence of the operator. The second and third processes led to savings in time and costs but also to the presence of voids with a void area fraction of 0.34% and 6.7%, respectively.

Uniaxial fatigue tests revealed a detrimental effect of voids on crack initiation and propagation and on the crack density evolution during fatigue life.

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